

On the Estimation of Three-Dimensional Porosity of Insect-Proof Screens

F.-J. Granados-Ortiz^a, F.M. Arrabal-Campos^{b,c}, A. Lopez-Martinez^{b,c,*}, F.D. Molina-Aiz^{b,c}, A. Peña-Fernández^{b,c}, D.L. Valera^{b,c}

^aDepartment of Mechanical, Thermal and Fluid Engineering, University of Málaga
C/ Dr Ortiz Ramos s/n, 29071 Málaga, Spain

^bDepartment of Engineering, University of Almería, Almería, Spain

^cCIAIMBITAL Research Centre, University of Almería, Almería, Spain

*Corresponding author: alexlopez@ual.es

Abstract

The two-dimensional estimation is the approach to porosity par excellence in the literature of insect-proof screens for their geometric characterisation and estimation of their aerodynamic parameters. However, this is not an accurate estimation, since the geometry of insect-proof screens consists of interlaced threads that create a three-dimensional woven structure, leading to different thicknesses and overlapping of threads. This paper suggests a mathematical approach to reconstruct computationally the 3D structure of the screens and to estimate the volumetric porosity, relying solely on easily measurable quantities such as diameter of threads, spacing of threads and thickness. The results on the application to 20+6 insect-proof screens in this work evidence that the suggested approach outperforms the standard two-dimensional modelling. These results also support experimental observations in the relationship between porosity and pressure drop not explainable by the two-dimensional approach. To increase the reliability on the analysis of porosity, the propagation of experimental uncertainty has been also included in the comparison between brand new and old&washed insect-proof screens. A software (Poro3D v1.0) using the methodology developed in this work is provided as supplementary material to this manuscript to instantly obtain both 3D and 2D porosities, as well as the reconstruction of 3D geometries.

Keywords: Insect-proof screens, Porosity, Aerodynamic characterisation, Woven fabric, Parametric surfaces

1. Introduction

Insect-proof screens are a physical method of crop protection that in recent decades has been extended and implemented in many countries, especially in Spain [1]. The textile industry estab-

lished the designation warp and weft because the screens are manufactured on totally flat looms. The width of the mesh is determined by the threads that are fixed on the loom, hence the name warp. The warp threads are divided into two groups of threads. The alternate separation set for these threads allows the shuttle to slide through the mesh crossing other threads called weft. In this way the loom is woven. They are installed in the lateral and zenithal ventilation openings of greenhouses, in order to prevent or reduce the entry of insects into the interior. Therefore, the choice of the type of insect-proof screen is conditioned by the size of the smaller pest species, whose presence inside the greenhouse is to be avoided [2].

Reducing insect populations inside a greenhouse provides great benefits by limiting direct damage to crops and disease transmissions, where insects are the main vectors of these diseases [3]. Another benefit derived is the reduction of treatment with phytosanitaries [4, 5], since this reduction of insect population is proportional to the quantity supplied for crop control [6, 7].

The use of insect-proof screens inside a greenhouse generates some problems related to ventilation, because it can be considered as an aerodynamic resistance. This yields that the exchange with the exterior is reduced and the bioclimatic environment [8, 9, 10, 11] inside the greenhouse is misaligned. This problem leads to a late development of the crop [12] and produces a favorable environment for the growth of fungal diseases [13, 14].

The physical description of the ventilation flow inside a greenhouse depends on the window geometry and the woven geometry of the insect-proof screen, as studied in [11, 15, 16, 17, 18]. This produces a pressure drop due to the circulation of air flow through a porous media. The pressure drop produced by insect-proof screens can be described by a quadratic relationship [15] dependent on the flow velocity (u). From this approximation, the aerodynamic behavior of the screen used can be determined by obtaining three experimental parameters F_ϕ , K_p and Y , where F_ϕ is pressure drop coefficient, K_p is the permeability and Y is the inertial factor.

The aerodynamic characteristics are estimated by performing wind tunnel tests. With these experiments, it is possible to develop models for predicting the pressure drop coefficient (F_ϕ) from the Reynolds number (Re_d) as a function of the average diameter of threads (D_h) and porosity (ϕ) [19]. These geometric parameters D_h and ϕ_{2D} (two-dimensional porosity) can be determined by digital image processing of insect-proof screens using computer vision techniques [20]. Actually, both geometrical parameters have been successfully measured in [21]. However, the direct measurement method is only valid to obtain the thread diameter and thickness of

62 the screen. A micrometer can be used to do this measurement. With the characteristics from
63 production process parameters and the diameter obtained, the porosity can be estimated [22].

64 Recent studies have developed different models to estimate the pressure drop caused by an
65 insect-proof screen at a specific air velocity from its geometric characteristics. The pressure drop
66 coefficient is estimated as a function of porosity and two options for the Reynolds number. The
67 Reynolds number is a critical parameter, since it can be calculated whether from the wire diameter
68 or from of the thickness [23]. The permeability and inertia factor can also be estimated from
69 different geometric parameters (K_p as a function of thread diameter and porosity; Y as a function
70 of thread diameter, and the inner pore diameter), and then K_p and Y can be used to obtain
71 the value of pressure drop [23]. These models have improved the estimation of these parameters
72 compared to previous models described in the literature [23]. However, this improvement is limited
73 by the estimation of the different geometric parameters required. Moreover, in the literature, screen
74 aerodynamics are entirely based on 2D porosity. However, a 3D porosity modeling of the screen
75 may overcome this limiting estimation by improving the characterisation.

76 There is an important dearth of literature on the 3D consideration of insect-proof screens. Most
77 works in the literature have considered screens as planar surfaces, as a consequence of orthogo-
78 nal projection [21, 23, 24], which is a simplification due to the complexity of their 3D structure.
79 Actually, three-dimensional efforts to date have been conducted to the calculation of the area
80 of the porous, leaving an accurate estimation of porosity behind, due to the interest in quanti-
81 fying the resistance to the pass of air through the porous openings. For instance, in [25] was
82 proposed to calculate the area of the porous from the orthogonally projected area of the 3D struc-
83 ture inside the porous. This approximation yielded high errors due to the non-linearity of the
84 hyperbolic paraboloid real area. An improvement of this calculation was carried out in [26] for
85 insect-proof screens. In this work, it was proposed an alternative method for estimating the area
86 of a three-dimensional porous. The spatial surface of the hole is defined by segments (generatri-
87 ces of threads adjacent to the porous), which define a parallelepiped based on the characteristic
88 geometric parameters L_{px} and L_{py} (horizontal spacing between threads in the x and y direction),
89 D_{hx} and D_{hy} (diameter of threads in the x and y direction), and thickness e (see Figure 1). This
90 method calculates the real surface improving the underestimated area of the porous in the two-
91 dimensional approach. Regarding the correct modelling of the 3D structure, several investigations
92 in the literature of woven fabrics proposed the use of an interlaced thread model as the work

93 on cloth structures developed by Peirce in [27]. This is the first work on theoretical modelling
94 of interlaced yarns, which considers threads as incompressible with circular cross-section. Other
95 researchers continued this work and extended the model to more advanced and complex shapes
96 such as [28], where mechanical deformation of threads was included; or the recent work in [29],
97 where Fourier series have been used to model the sinusoidal-like shape of very complex multi-layer
98 threads. Structural properties of 3D woven fabrics have been also studied numerically using the
99 Finite Element Method (FEM), see for instance [30]. A comprehensive review on the analysis of
100 the mechanical properties of these structures can be found in [31]. Also, in other works such as
101 [32], Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) are used to study the pressure drop in textile fabrics
102 using 3D models with circular and elliptic cross-sections, which evidence the importance of the
103 availability of 3D shapes of insect-proof screens for further computational investigation. None of
104 the aforementioned 3D studies (except [26]) were oriented to application in insect-proof screens,
105 and there are no works in the literature on the estimation of porosity from a 3D view. The 2D
106 porosity modelling of screens is the standard approach even in recent applications in the literature
107 such as e.g. [23, 24, 33, 34].

108 Herein, we introduce a novel solution to estimate porosity of insect-proof screens as a three-
109 dimensional property for the first time in the literature. This estimation is grounded on the
110 mathematical reconstruction of the porous volume and based on the measurable characteristic
111 geometric parameters L_{px} , L_{py} , D_{hx} , D_{hy} , and e . In order to improve the reliability of this research,
112 an analysis of the propagation of experimental uncertainty in the model has been included. The
113 results yield that the theoretical estimations are consistent with the experimental observations.
114 This theoretical approach will be crucial for the estimation of the aerodynamic characteristics inside
115 a greenhouse by making accurate estimations of the physical parameters, F_ϕ , K_p and Y . In fact,
116 this three-dimensional model sheds light on the behaviour of pressure drop observed in experimental
117 tests (pressure drop decreases as porosity increases), not explainable by two-dimensional porosity.
118 Thus, this approach will improve the prediction and quantification of the effectiveness of screens
119 against insects and fungal diseases by enhancing the control of the bioclimatic environment of
120 the crop within greenhouses. In addition, with accurate estimates of 3D porosity, and also its 3D
121 geometric reconstruction, it will be possible to select the right type of screen to exclude a particular
122 type of pest but aiming at a decent high porosity at the same time. The methodology and codes
123 resulting from this work have been implemented in the Poro3D v1.0 software, which is provided

124 as supplementary material to this manuscript.

125 The present paper has been structured as follows: Section 2 is dedicated to describe the method-
126 ology pursued in this investigation. In Section 3, details on the mathematical foundations of
127 the theoretical approach are given, covering aspects such as the model of the interlaced threads,
128 parametrisation of the volumes, and calculation of superficial and volumetric porosity. In Section
129 4, the results from the application of the model to real insect-proof screens are presented. This in-
130 cludes the effect of ageing in the screens, by including an uncertainty quantification study. Finally,
131 in Section 5 the most relevant conclusions from the present work are given.

Figure 1: Dimensions of an insect-proof screen.

132 2. Methodology

133 The methodology followed in this work consists of three stages. First, the geometric param-
134 eters of the insect-proof screen under consideration are measured in the laboratory by means of
135 microscope images (which can be processed by a dedicated software [21]). These values are input
136 parameters to the equations to be solved numerically. Although the more the measured parameters
137 the better, some may be hard to measure, such as the crisp of a thread or certain angles. Thus, to
138 facilitate the measurement task, the models are adapted to require only the diameter of threads,
139 spacing between threads, thickness of the screen, and to specify whether the outer threads are
140 those in the x or y direction.

141 Second, a non-linear model is solved with an iterative approach by means of a numerical code.
 142 The code uses the geometric parameters as input and estimates the slope of the threads, the
 143 portion in contact between threads, and their total lengths. This also allows to reconstruct the
 144 three-dimensional shape of the interlacing threads, which is also provided by the numerical code
 145 for visualisation.

146 Third, by using the solution from the previous step, the volumetric porosity can be estimated as
 147 the ratio between the volume of threads and total volume. These volumes are calculated by means
 148 of the integral of parametrisation volumes. Since during the measurement stage experimental
 149 uncertainty has been also identified, its propagation in the model and estimation of volumetric
 150 porosity can be also quantified by means of a random/pseudo-random sampling (or any suitable
 151 sampling or quadrature-based method). This leads not only to the estimation of a value of porosity,
 152 but also the impact of experimental uncertainty in the calculation, which may be of interest in a
 153 comparison between new and old screens.

154 3. Mathematical Considerations

155 In this section, the mathematical details of the non-linear model of the threads interlacing, the
 156 parametrisation of volumes and calculation of volumetric porosity are given. The validation of the
 157 models is also included in this section.

158 3.1. Thread Interlacing Model

159 The model for cloth woven structures first suggested by Peirce [27] is used in this work. This
 160 model consists of assuming that a woven fabric is composed of inextensible, incompressible and
 161 fully round cross-section threads. This is an accurate representation for insect-proof screens, since
 162 these are regularly made of High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) monofilament-woven fabrics [33].
 163 Thus, the objective in this work is to adapt such mathematical model to the geometry of insect-
 164 proof screens, which are usually characterised in the literature experimentally by the diameter of
 165 the interlaced threads, their spacing and the thickness [23, 21, 33]. Peirce [27] suggested that a
 166 woven fabric can be modelled by means of seven equations connecting eleven quantities. These
 167 equations are:

$$c_i = \frac{l_i}{p_i} - 1, \quad (1)$$

$$p_i = (l_i - D\theta_i) \cos \theta_i + D \sin \theta_i \quad (2)$$

$$h_i = (l_i - D\theta_i) \sin \theta_i + D(1 - \cos \theta_i), \quad (3)$$

$$D = h_x + h_y, \quad (4)$$

171 where c_i is the fractional crimp, l_i is the total length of the thread, p_i is the horizontal spacing of
 172 threads, θ_i is the angle with respect to the horizontal plane, and h_i is the vertical displacement
 173 of the threads. The subscript $i = x, y$ represents a specific thread direction thread (in the present
 174 work, x is used for quantities related to the x -coordinate, and y for quantities in the y -coordinate)
 175 as shown in Figure 2).

Figure 2: Sketch of Peirce's woven fabric model applied to insect-proof screens characterisation.

176 Amongst the eleven quantities required to fully describe the geometry of the threads, only the
 177 spacings p_i (in Figure 2 can be seen that $p_y = L_{px} + D_{hy}$) are known. In previous works in the
 178 literature, authors that characterised insect-proof screens usually only rely on the diameter of the
 179 threads (D_{hx}, D_{hy}), their horizontal spacing between threads (L_{px}, L_{py}) and the thickness (e). This
 180 is so because there are actually software that provide these data from images (see for instance [21]).
 181 The total length l_i of a thread is formed by the combination of a straight part of length L_i and two
 182 curved sides enveloping the orthogonal threads. This is the reason of the equation for the crimp
 183 (Equation (1)). To closure the mathematical problem, for instance in Equation (1) the crimp or
 184 total length should be known, but these quantities are complex to be obtained experimentally.
 185 Also, the process may be cumbersome if many insect-proof screens are under study without a
 186 dedicated software to measure l_i .

187 An efficient alternative is to estimate the values of the vertical distances h_x and h_y based
 188 solely on the thickness of the screen and the configuration. Alternative forms of the two equations
 189 compacted in Equation (3) can be found by trigonometric relations in Figure 2, yielding:

$$h_y = \frac{(D_{hx} + D_{hy})}{\cos \theta_x} - (L_{px} + D_{hy}) \tan \theta_x, \quad (5)$$

$$h_x = (D_{hx} + D_{hy}) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\cos \theta_x}\right) + (L_{px} + D_{hy}) \tan \theta_x. \quad (6)$$

191 By using these equations, one can get rid of Equation (4). However, h_x and h_y are still unknown.
 192 Although these parameters can be related to the thickness e in Figure 2, this cannot be generalised
 193 for any insect-proof screen. This is because if the top and bottom threads (outer threads) are those
 194 that correspond to the orthogonal threads denoted by $i = y$, then the relations are different. This
 195 is depicted in Figure 3. For this reason, to closure the problem by obtaining h_x and h_y with
 196 relations with the thickness e , the practitioner must classify beforehand whether the insect-proof
 197 screen corresponds to *configuration 1* (Figure 2) or *configuration 2* (Figure 3). As rule of thumb,
 198 the *configuration 1* is also valid if both threads are at the same height. If the type of configuration
 199 is not provided, the system of equations would not have a unique solution for $\theta_i \in [0, 2\pi)$. The
 200 relations to calculate h_x and h_y are thus:

201
 202 *Configuration 1:*

$$\begin{aligned} h_x &= e - D_{hx}, \\ h_y &= 2D_{hx} + D_{hy} - e, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

203 *Configuration 2:*

$$\begin{aligned} h_x &= 2D_{hy} + D_{hx} - e, \\ h_y &= e - D_{hy}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

204 Obviously, another simple and equivalent solution could be to only consider, for instance the
 205 expressions given for *configuration 1*, and select the thread indices i accordingly. However, in
 206 many insect-proof screens, the pores are rectangles longer in the y -axis than the x -axis, thus the
 207 subscript of the threads is assumed to be known beforehand.

208 With all the aforementioned reductions on the model equations, it is now possible to solve
 209 the system of non-linear equations. For this task, a MATLAB script is coded, which solves the
 210 system of non-linear equations iteratively with a convergence criteria of 10^{-10} . The code has been

Figure 3: Example of y -axis threads ($i = y$) on top and bottom (outer threads) of the insect-proof screen (namely configuration 2).

211 validated with images from the laboratory, as will be also shown in Section 3.2 after introducing
 212 all the aspects of the code.

213 Once the script provides the geometric values, the volumes can be parametrised. Specially
 214 important are θ_x and θ_y for this objective, since these values set the slope of the straight portion
 215 of the thread and the portion of curved envelopes on the warp threads, as will be shown next.

216 3.2. Parametrisation of Threads.

217 In order to calculate the volumetric porosity, the geometry of the threads has been parametrised.
 218 This allows to visualise the correctness of the shapes, as well as to calculate the volumes of interest.
 219 These parametrisations are developed upon the solved non-linear equations with the in-house
 220 MATLAB code. The full periodic geometry consists of a cylinder with a slope θ_i , and two portions
 221 of toroids, tangential to the cross threads.

222 It is well-known that a cylinder of length L_i centered in the origin and around the x -axis can
 223 be expressed by using parametric equations in cylindrical coordinates as

$$\begin{aligned}
 x(L, s) &= L, \\
 y(L, s) &= r \cos s, \text{ with } L \in [-L_i/2, L_i/2] \text{ and } s \in [0, 2\pi), \\
 z(L, s) &= r \sin s,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

224 where r is the radius of the cylinder and L_i is the total length. However, the pieces of cylinder
 225 used to model the straight parts of the threads are not horizontal but have a slope θ_i (let us use
 226 θ hereinafter for the sake of simplicity). When a geometry is rotated, a rotation matrix must be

227 used to guarantee the conservation of the shape. For a degree of rotation θ around the y -axis, the
 228 rotation matrix obtained by considering the necessary trigonometric relations is

$$M_r = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & 0 & \sin \theta \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & 0 & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

229 This matrix allows to rewrite the parametric equations of the cylinder as:

$$\begin{aligned} x'(L, s) &= L \cos \theta + r \sin s \sin \theta, \\ y'(L, s) &= r \cos s, \text{ with } L \in [-L_i/2, L_i/2] \text{ and } s \in [0, 2\pi), \\ z'(L, s) &= r \sin s \cos \theta - L \sin \theta. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

230 In these equations the signs of the second summation terms at the right hand side of x' and y'
 231 can be inverted to consider $\theta > 0$ in the anticlockwise direction. It is obvious that the parametric
 232 equations must be customised accordingly to plot the different positions (spacing between threads)
 233 and orientations (θ_x and θ_y) of the threads.

234 In the geometric simplification shown in Figure 2 each thread also contains two toroid portions:
 235 one below the first orthogonal thread of diameter D_{hx} , and another above the second orthogonal
 236 thread of the same diameter. These portions of toroidal volume are concentric and tangential to
 237 the said threads, thus the reconstruction of the volume is simple once all the geometric parameters
 238 are known. For instance, in the geometry given in Figure 2, the positions of the centers of the
 239 toroids will be given by $O_1(-L_{px}/2 - D_{hy}/2, h_y/2)$ and $O_2(L_{px}/2 + D_{hy}/2, -h_y/2)$ for the first and
 240 second thread, respectively. Upon this, for instance, on a xz -plane view, the parametric equations
 241 of the portion of toroid in cylindrical coordinates can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} x'(u, v) &= (a + R \cos v) \cos u + O_{ix}, \\ y'(u, v) &= R \sin v, \text{ with } v \in [0, 2\pi) \text{ and } u \in [k, \theta + k), \\ z'(u, v) &= (a + R \cos v) \sin u + O_{iz}, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

242 with a the position with respect to the reference origin, R the radius of a circular section of the
 243 toroid, θ the slope of the cylinder, and O_{ix} and O_{iz} the x and z coordinates of the center of the
 244 toroid for the thread i , respectively. Must be noted that k is a parameter required to control the
 245 beginning and the end of the angle spanned by the toroid. For instance, in a sketch such as Figure
 246 2, the first portion of toroid is developed according to $k = 3\pi/2$, and the second portion, according

247 to $k = \pi/2$. As in the explanation provided for the cylinder, the parametric equations of the
 248 portions of toroid must be adapted to, for instance, each y position by adding to y' the distance
 249 between threads. The process is homologous in the a yz -plane view.

250 By taking into account all the aforementioned parametric equations, a 3D view of the insect-
 251 proof screen thread interlacing can be reconstructed. This has been added to the numerical code,
 252 and the results are shown in Figure 4. In addition, 2D views are generated, which can be seen in
 253 Figure 5. Note that the cross section of the threads is a perfect circle, but the figure may show a
 254 elliptic-like shape due to the automatic selection of the axis limits in the visualisation of the figure.
 255 To be able to construct by parametrisation the 3D geometry is of strong interest for instance for
 256 computational design of new threads by means of Computational (Fluid) Mechanics [35, 36].

Figure 4: 3D view of the insect-proof screen threads.

257 A validation of the code has been developed. For a realistic validation of the thread interlacing
 258 generated, the geometric details of three insect-proof screens in Lopez et al. [23] have been input
 259 to the MATLAB code to check the accuracy in the reconstruction of real insect-proof screens.
 260 Upon experimental measurements and images taken in the laboratory, it is known that the config-
 261 uration of the threads is *Configuration 2*. Several Image Recognition algorithms have been used
 262 in MATLAB to detect the edges in the microscope images (4X lens with a calibration of 10.52632
 263 micron/pixel) of the interlaced yarns in order to perform a fair comparison. The Prewitt method
 264 calculates the gradients of the image by means of the Prewitt algorithm [37] to approximate the
 265 derivative. The regions of highest gradients are recognised as edges. Such derivatives can be

Figure 5: 2D views of the interlacing of the insect-proof screen threads.

266 also approximated by the Sobel operator [38], which calculates gradient point by point with some
 267 smoothing effect of random noise; or the Roberts operator, which applies a discrete differentiation
 268 algorithm to compute the differences between adjacent pixels [39]. The *Log* edge detection filters
 269 the image with a Laplacian of Gaussian filter (LoG), hence the name. The Gaussian filter is useful
 270 to smooth the random noise in the image, which is also another advantage in the Canny algorithm
 271 [40]. The results of the application of these algorithms are shown in Figure 6. In this figure can
 272 be seen that only the *Canny* method was able to detect the edges of the threads perpendicular
 273 to the view plane. This is because this method uses a multi-step approach with the derivatives
 274 of a Gaussian filter and detects strong and weak edges. It is the most recommended method for
 275 edge detection amongst practitioners, despite is more computationally expensive. This is the only
 276 method amongst the tested ones that is able to detect weak edges if these are connected to strong
 277 edges. This is the reason of detecting a clearer delimitation of the blurred circular sections. The
 278 mathematical details of each method are not to be described in the present manuscript, as they
 279 are used as mere tools in this work and there is a vast amount of literature on their description.

280 The reconstructed geometry is compared with the regular image and *Canny* edge detection
 281 method in Figure 7. In this figure, the *yz* view is shown (one view is enough for validation as
 282 both views depend on each other) for the regular image and edge detection. On top of these, the
 283 calculated geometry by the MATLAB code is shown in yellow and red, in order to distinguish each
 284 line. The resulting geometry shows an outstanding match with the actual insect-proof screens,
 285 despite of the assumptions of the model (round cross-section, incompressible threads, straight

286 threads). Must be recalled that the modelled threads are assumed to have perfect round sections,
 287 but the actual threads may have some deformation due to the tension force. Nevertheless, such
 288 change in section is not expected to be very remarkable in a HDPE yarn, as evidenced in the
 validation.

Figure 6: Detection of the edges in the image of the insect-proof screen n.1 in Lopez et al. [23]

289

290 3.3. Calculation of Volumetric Porosity

291 Previous works in the literature have been focused on porosity of insect-proof screens as a 2D
 292 approach. For instance, Alvarez et al. [21] used a software to estimate the porosity from pictures
 293 of screen threads. The porosity is calculated as shown in Equation (13):

$$\phi_{2D} = \frac{A_p}{A_t} = \frac{L_{px}L_{py}}{(L_{px} + D_{hy})(L_{py} + D_{hx})}, \quad (13)$$

294 where ϕ_{2D} stands for the two-dimensional porosity (in $[m^2/m^2]$ units), A_p is the total pore surface,
 295 and A_t is the total area. For instance in [41, 33], this porosity is used to study the effect of ageing
 296 and dirt on insect-proof screens. Another important application of this superficial porosity is found
 297 in Lopez et al. [23], where this porosity is used to develop models for the aerodynamic performance
 298 of insect-proof screens. A similar aerodynamic characterisation is developed by Perez et al. [24] or
 299 Castellano et al. [42], amongst many others. Wang and coworkers also analysed computationally in
 300 [32] the pressure drop in textile fabrics using 3D models, opposite to the traditional 2D simplified
 301 computational approach.

302 The important drawback implicit in a two-dimensional estimation of porosity is that the effect
 303 of the thickness is not taken into account. These works consider the insect-proof screen as a
 304 geometry of negligible thickness, and do not consider the thickness of the screen nor the overlap
 305 of yarns in the z -coordinate. Thus, a superficial estimation of porosity is an useful but inaccurate

(a) Estimated geometry n.1 in yellow.

(b) Estimated geometry n.1 in red.

(c) Estimated geometry n.2 in yellow.

(d) Estimated geometry n.2 in red.

(e) Estimated geometry n.14 in yellow.

(f) Estimated geometry n.14 in red.

Figure 7: Validation of the estimated geometry of insect-proof screens. The screens are those numbered as n.1 [(a) and (b)], n.2 [(c) and (d)] and n.14 [(e) and (f)] in Lopez et al. [23], as these represent a density of threads of $\rho_t = [11 \times 23]$, $[10 \times 20]$ and $[14 \times 27]$, respectively.

306 approach to insect-proof screens. The importance of the 3D shape in insect-proof screens has been
 307 first considered only in the calculation of the size of the pore in [43]. However, this work only
 308 considered the size of the pore as a 2D surface corresponding to the 3D deformation in space of a
 309 rectangular pore. They did not provide new estimations of porosity, but suggested that to follow
 310 a 3D approach is more accurate.

311 To estimate a volumetric porosity, the equivalent to superficial porosity can be considered by

312 calculating the ratio between the volume of the pore and the total volume (see Figure 8):

$$\phi_{3D} = \frac{V_p}{V_t} = 1 - \frac{V_h}{V_t}, \quad (14)$$

313 where ϕ_{3D} stands for the volumetric porosity (in $[m^3/m^3]$ units), V_p is the total pore volume, V_t is
 314 the total volume, and V_h is the total volume filled by the threads. This expression is developed upon
 315 the fact that the total volume of the pore can be computed from the difference between the total
 volume and the volume of the threads. The volumes of the threads are computed straightforward.

Figure 8: 3D view of the considered volume of the insect-proof screen for the estimation of the volumetric porosity.

316
 317 The half of the volume of the cylinders are inside the total volume depicted in solid black line
 318 in Figure 8. Their volume can be hence computed as $V_{cil} = 1/8\pi D^2 L_i$, with D the diameter of
 319 the thread and L_i the length. On the other hand, the volume of the portion of toroid must be
 320 computed from integration. Let us consider a generic toroid from Equation (12) but centered in
 321 $O(0, 0, 0)$, with $v \in [0, \pi]$ and $u \in [0, \theta]$. The volume of the portion of the halved toroid that is
 322 developed according to θ can be computed as

$$V_{tor} = \int_0^\pi \int_0^\theta \int_0^R r(a + r \cos v) dr du dv = \frac{1}{2} \pi R^2 a \theta, \quad (15)$$

323 where the Jacobian has been calculated from

$$J(u, v, R) = \left| \frac{\partial(x', y', z')}{\partial(u, v, R)} \right| = R(a + R \cos v). \quad (16)$$

324 Thus, the calculation of the volumetric porosity can be estimated by the code (upon the geometric
 325 parameters shown in Figure 2) by including all the volumes in Equation (14) as:

$$\phi_{3D} = 1 - \pi \frac{D_{hx} L_x + D_{hx}^2 (D_{hx} + D_{hy}) \theta_x + D_{hy} L_y + D_{hy}^2 (D_{hx} + D_{hy}) \theta_y}{4e(L_{px} + D_{hy})(L_{py} + D_{hx})}, \quad (17)$$

326 where $e, L_{px}, L_{py}, D_{hx}$ and D_{hy} are inputs given from measurements, and θ_x, θ_y, L_x and L_y are
 327 calculated from the inputs by the code. This resulting equation in (17) is interesting not only
 328 to provide a three-dimensional porosity upon the said measurements and calculation, but it also
 329 enables to estimate the volumetric porosity if θ_x and θ_y are measured at the laboratory from
 330 microscope images.

331 4. Results and Discussion

332 In this section the models are tested in the estimation of porosity of real insect-proof screens, in
 333 order to analyse the differences between a two-dimensional and three-dimensional approach. This
 334 includes the application to a large number of screens, as well as a quantification of the impact of
 335 ageing in the estimation of both porosities.

336 4.1. Volumetric Porosity of Insect-Proof Screens

337 The proposed method to quantify the volumetric porosity in insect-proof screens has been
 338 applied to several screens previously measured in the laboratory. Concretely, volumetric porosity
 339 has been calculated for 20 insect-proof screens (IPS) from Lopez et al. [23], whose results are
 340 provided in Table 1. The 20 IPS selected consist of a set of screens that cover an interesting
 341 amount of assorted representative densities of threads (ρ_t) used in Mediterranean greenhouses.
 342 A visual comparison between the two-dimensional (ϕ_{2D}) and three-dimensional (ϕ_{3D}) porosities
 343 is given in Figure 9. In the figure, data is clustered according to thread density and ordered in
 344 ascending order of ϕ_{2D} , which is useful to detect differences in the trend between ϕ_{2D} and ϕ_{3D} .
 345 In this figure is observed that there is a notable resemblance in the plot between both porosities
 346 (which provides additional confidence in our results), but at the same time volumetric porosity
 347 seems to correct certain deficiencies in the superficial porosity approach.

348 To better understand the goodness of the 3D approach, in Figure 10 is shown the effect of an
 349 univariate variation of a $\pm 7\%$ in the thickness of three characteristic IPS of each thread density
 350 group ρ_t , the $N_{IPS} = 4, 16$ and 20 . In spite of the variation of the thickness does not vary ϕ_{2D} , it
 351 is obvious that ϕ_{3D} varies. This increase in thickness can actually generate feasible geometries, as
 352 Figures 11 and 12 show for $N_{IPS} = 4$ and 20 . It can be observed that, as the thickness is increased,
 353 θ_x decreases and θ_y increases (in a screen with *Configuration 1* would happen the opposite), in
 354 order to adapt the threads to the new geometry.

N_{IPS}	N (as in [23])	ρ_t	L_{px}	L_{py}	D_{hx}	D_{hy}	e	ϕ_{2D}	ϕ_{3D}
1	15	14×27	131.84	570.46	209.6	225.74	489.82	0.2700	0.6548
2	14	14×27	141.8	615.93	214.81	221.73	514.28	0.2880	0.6876
3	9	14×27	187.33	543.47	186.45	183.97	417.75	0.3790	0.7233
4	26	14×27	188.4	591.6	184.1	184.7	401.7	0.3850	0.7207
5	25	10×20	233.7	734	276.4	273.4	563.8	0.3350	0.6642
6	4	10×20	226.87	681.08	256.83	243.52	566.62	0.3490	0.7092
7	30	10×20	238.57	745.95	272	261.24	564.4	0.3497	0.6877
8	35	10×20	239.99	761.46	263.95	261.81	534.67	0.3541	0.6774
9	3	10×20	232.48	760.74	233.06	253.08	544.35	0.3660	0.7153
10	13	10×20	252.74	746.43	258.95	255.66	639.22	0.3680	0.7453
11	2	10×20	243.71	773.99	251.59	253.5	595.82	0.3690	0.7337
12	12	10×20	250.31	865.1	264.6	260.28	610.55	0.3750	0.7360
13	27	10×20	234.9	838.7	245.8	248	525.91	0.3750	0.7107
14	10	10×20	253.89	784.27	250.54	253.49	586.68	0.3790	0.7351
15	28	10×20	256.6	736.4	256.8	243.7	480.19	0.3790	0.6741
16	8	10×20	246.76	877.27	233.8	236.45	545.95	0.4020	0.7519
17	31	15×30	107.52	456.34	195.99	211.07	507.52	0.2365	0.6626
18	29	13×30	110.02	611.88	187.7	209.4	458.13	0.2634	0.6673
19	22	13×30	170.9	876.8	163.3	160	406.07	0.4370	0.7951
20	17	15×30	221.6	548.8	110.5	109.9	260.57	0.5560	0.8302

Table 1: Estimation of volumetric porosity of 20 representative insect-proof screens in Lopez et al. [23]. All units are given in micrometers (10^{-6} meters). All screens are interlaced according to Configuration 2. N is the number of IPS in [23] and N_{IPS} is the numeration in the present paper.

355 It is important to note that the increase in thickness has a different impact on each IPS. Whilst
356 a variation of a $\pm 7\%$ in e leads to a relative variation ($\frac{\phi_{3D,max} - \phi_{3D,min}}{\phi_{3D}}$) of a 5.8% for $N_{IPS} = 4$, the
357 impact is halved for $N_{IPS} = 20$, being a 2.9%. For $N_{IPS} = 16$, the impact is a 4.7% of variation.
358 Thus, this illustrates that there are important non-linear interactions between the 3D geometric
359 design parameters and ϕ_{3D} (as expected due to the nature of Equation (14)), opposite to the
360 simplified equation for ϕ_{2D} . This explains the differences in trend of ϕ_{2D} and ϕ_{3D} in Figure 9 and

Figure 9: Comparison plot between ϕ_{2D} and ϕ_{3D} .

361 highlights the importance of a 3D approach for porosity characterisation of insect-proof screens.
 362 The sensitivity of ϕ_{3D} to e could be easily obtained analytically from partial derivative of Equation
 363 (14) if an analytical solution of θ_x and θ_y is available, which is not the case to our knowledge.

Figure 10: Impact of increasing/decreasing thickness in insect-proof screens.

364 4.2. Effect of Ageing in the Estimation of Volumetric Porosity

365 An important issue in insect-proof screens is their deterioration as a consequence of ageing,
 366 as pointed out in [33]. The mesh of the screen becomes less tense, thus the diameter of the
 367 threads and thickness is slightly increased and the original geometry design suffers some variation.
 368 This affects to their aerodynamic behaviour, spotting differences between their new and aged
 369 performance [41, 33]. The changes in the structure of the insect-proof screen will thus have an
 370 impact on the estimation of the two-dimensional and three-dimensional porosity. Uncertainty in
 371 the measurements is also subject to such variability, which is expected to be increased in older

Figure 11: Impact on geometry of increasing/decreasing thickness in insect-proof screen $N_{IPS} = 4$.

Figure 12: Impact on geometry of increasing/decreasing thickness in insect-proof screen $N_{IPS} = 20$.

372 screens. For these reasons, uncertainty quantification can be used to estimate accurately the
 373 impact of ageing in the porosity of the insect-proof screen, by including measurement and ageing
 374 uncertainty. Although dirt insect-proof screens may be considered for this analysis, the uneven
 375 contribution to uncertainty may be misleading, thus this is not considered. Such contribution
 376 is uneven in the sense that, for instance, dirt may increase the thickness of the screen, but the
 377 diameter of the threads would not be evenly increased (for instance, there is no dirt in the contact
 378 surface between threads, etc.). Thence, to study numerically the contribution to uncertainty by
 379 dirtiness would not be realistic with our numerical model.

380 In the present work, the calculation of the insect-proof screen porosity starts with inputs from
 381 measurements, and later these are used to calculate the full set of geometric parameters that
 382 characterise the screens. However, the impact of uncertainty due to fabrication tolerances, aging

383 or measurement tolerances may be important in order to quantify the sensitivity of the porosity
 384 to the input uncertainty and make a fair comparison. The objective of uncertainty quantification
 385 is “to provide confidence measures on how the output of a model is varied due to the variability
 386 of its inputs” [44, 45]. This field has gained increasing interest in recent years in applications such
 387 as complex fluid dynamics [46], ventilation [47], heat transfer [48], or weather forecasting [49],
 388 amongst many others.

389 The first step in the study of the propagation of uncertainty is to model input uncertainty.
 390 For this purpose, realistic random variables have been modelled for e , L_{px} , L_{py} , D_{hx} , and D_{hy} .
 391 The measurement data for this modelling corresponds to three insect-proof screens (six studies
 392 in total), whose *New* and *Old&Washed* geometric data is provided in [33] (and also in Table 2).
 393 According to the central limit theorem, these sources of uncertainty follow a normal distribution,
 394 which is written as follows in compact notation for each random variable ξ_i :

$$\xi_i \sim N(\bar{\xi}_i, \sigma_{\xi_i}), \quad (18)$$

395 where $\bar{\xi}_i$ stands for the mean value of the parameter ξ_i , and σ_{ξ_i} for the standard deviation of each
 396 distribution. This uncertainty quantification has been applied to the six aforementioned insect-
 397 proof screens. Upon the modelling of input uncertainty, the five probabilistic distributions of e , L_{px} ,
 398 L_{py} , D_{hx} and D_{hy} are pseudorandomly sampled with a large number of samples ($N = 20000$) to
 399 ensure convergence of the method. It has been tested that this number of samples is enough in our
 400 numerical tests. We refer to the sampling as pseudorandom due to the geometric constrains of the
 401 problem that lead us to apply constrains to the randomness. Since the sampling is done supposing
 402 each parameter as independent, some samples may lead to unfeasible geometries (combinations
 403 of the input parameters that do not lead to a realistic geometry) or changes in the configuration
 404 (a baseline *configuration 1* may change to *configuration 2* if the size of the threads in the new
 405 sample obliges so). These inconveniences can be solved by performing sampling based on relations
 406 between the input random variables, but the only relations available are the Equations (1)-(4),
 407 which are to be solved in the process. However, it is possible to detect and discard incorrect
 408 samples (mathematically possible but physically unfeasible) by taking into account some basic
 409 geometric relations. Thus, the sampling has been constrained by the following conditions:

- 410 • The maximum thickness that can be achieved in the insect-proof screen is either $2D_{hx} + D_{hy}$
 411 for *configuration 1* (condition 1) or $2D_{hy} + D_{hx}$ for *configuration 2* (condition 2). Thus, in

412 each sample, either condition 1 or condition 2 must be greater or equal to the actual e in the
 413 sample. If this criteria is not matched, the geometry is not realistic.

- 414 • The threads are interlaced. Thus, the separation between threads must be at least equal
 415 to the diameter of the interlaced thread, otherwise the geometry is not realistic. This is
 416 constrained by the relations (see Figure 13): $\frac{h_x}{\sin \gamma_x} - D_{hx} \leq D_{hy}$ and $\frac{h_y}{\sin \gamma_y} - D_{hy} \leq D_{hx}$,
 417 where $\gamma_i = \text{atan}(\frac{h_i}{L_{pj} + D_{hi}})$ with $i = x, y$.

N (type)	$L_{px} \pm \sigma_{L_{px}}$	$L_{py} \pm \sigma_{L_{py}}$	$D_{hx} \pm \sigma_{D_{hx}}$	$D_{hy} \pm \sigma_{D_{hy}}$	$e \pm \sigma_e$
1 (n)	164.6 ± 9.3	593.3 ± 19	168.6 ± 6.6	163.1 ± 6.3	391.7 ± 5.3
1 (ow)	156.5 ± 10.7	574.6 ± 19.3	170.5 ± 6	169.3 ± 6	415.6 ± 41.7
2 (n)	234.9 ± 16.1	838.7 ± 27	245.8 ± 7.1	248 ± 8.3	525.9 ± 27.6
2 (ow)	225.8 ± 16.2	828.4 ± 22.5	257 ± 5.3	256.9 ± 8.7	627.9 ± 38.2
3 (n)	256.6 ± 14.3	736.4 ± 17.1	256.8 ± 8.3	243.7 ± 8.2	480.2 ± 11.2
3 (ow)	244.1 ± 15.6	716 ± 23.0	256.7 ± 11.2	252.3 ± 9.4	559.1 ± 50.8

Table 2: Measured geometric parameters (mean value \pm standard deviation) of three *New* (n) and *Old&Washed* (ow) insect-proof screens from [33]. All units are given in micrometers (10^{-6} meters).

(a) Sketch to quantify the separation between threads. (b) Example of unfeasible sampled geometry. .

Figure 13: Necessary separation conditions of a sample for a physically permissible geometry.

418 Due to the uncertainty ranges considered in this work are related to real experimental mea-
 419 surements of clean insect-proof screens, these are not very large. Therefore, it is not frequent to

420 obtain samples that violate the above mentioned geometric constrains. This usually happened in
421 very few samples in the tail of the probabilistic distributions of the *Old&Washed* screens. Results
422 from the sampling for the insect-proof screen number 1 are shown in Figure 14. The *Old&Washed*
423 screen number 1 was the one with more unfeasible geometries (but only circa 500 out of 20000).
424 In Figure 14 this is noted by observing some cuts in the tail of the distributions of e . As observed,
425 the number of unfeasible geometries is not relevant, but these are discarded from the analysis as
426 their output uncertainty is unreal.

427 In Figure 15 are depicted the output uncertainty results from the analysis of the same insect-
428 proof screen. It is interesting to note that despite the non-linear relations between input parame-
429 ters, the output results also follow normal distributions, especially in the *New* insect-proof screens,
430 possibly because the geometry is more robust (lower input uncertainty range, thus less geometries
431 transitioned between *configuration 1* and *2*, no unfeasible geometries discarded, etc.). In Figure
432 15.(b) can be observed that the *Old&Washed* geometry still preserved the normal distribution
433 shape, but the ϕ_{3D} distribution has certain level of skewness. Must be noted that the distribution
434 of the angle θ_x has its tail cut for $\theta_x < 0$, because unfeasible geometries yield negative values of
435 the angle to satisfy the equations mathematically, but this is not physically correct. It is also
436 observed an important impact on the stochastic standard deviation of relevant parameters such as
437 the angles θ_x and θ_y (in degrees). These parameters exhibit an important range of variation (which
438 is acceptable, as the inclination of the threads is subject to strong variability as the separation
439 and diameters change), which impacts on the calculation of the volumetric porosity.

440 Finally, the results from this uncertainty analysis for the six screens are shown in Figure 16. In
441 the figure are compared the results of the calculation of superficial and volumetric porosities. In
442 this comparison one can observe an important fact: in the calculation of 2D porosity, the porosity
443 of new screens is greater than the porosity of old and washed screens, as already shown in [33].
444 However, in the calculation of the volumetric porosity, the scenario is the opposite: the old insect-
445 proof screen porosity is greater than the porosity of new screens. In the works from the literature
446 where new and old screens have been compared, such as [33, 41, 50], they observed that with
447 ageing, the pressure drop of air passing through the screens is decreased in comparison to new
448 insect-proof screens. More concretely, in [33] *New* and *Old&Washed* screens were studied, and it
449 was noticed that the pressure drop was greater for new screens than for the old and washed ones,
450 despite the fact that the (two-dimensional) porosity was greater for new insect-proof screens. The

Figure 14: Pseudorandom sampling with $N = 20000$ samples for insect-proof screen n.1 from Table 2.

451 results shown in our analysis thus evidence that ϕ_{3D} is a more realistic representation of porosity
 452 of an insect-proof screen, as evidenced in Figure 16. This is evident in the sense that the loss of
 453 tension in the threads with time and ageing is assumed to lead to a light increase in the diameter
 454 of threads and thickness. The two-dimensional approach does not include any effect of thickness
 455 in the porosity, thus the results are doubtful. The calculation shown in this manuscript certifies

456 the expected fact that, as the volumetric porosity increases, the pressure drop decreases. Another
 457 relevant observation is that the range of variation (uncertainty bars) is more remarkable for the
 458 *Old&Washed* screens compared to the *New* screens in the 3D porosity, which may be a result
 459 of the greater magnitude of volumetric variations. That is to say, if the radius of a thread is
 460 increased, for instance, a 10% in the *Old&Washed* screen due to the lower tension forces, in terms
 461 of superficial calculation its increase would be $(1.1R)^2$; whereas the volumetric growth is of order
 462 $(1.1R)^3$. Therefore, a volumetric estimation of porosity is also a more complete picture of the
 463 impact of ageing in the insect-proof screen in this sense.

(a) New.

(b) Old&Washed.

Figure 15: Uncertainty quantification results with $N = 20000$ pseudorandom samples and probabilistic distribution fits for insect-proof screen number 1 from Table 2

Figure 16: Comparison between *New* and *Old&Washed* insect-proof screens to analyse the effect of ageing in the estimation of porosity. The errorbars are the mean values \pm standard deviation. Insect-proof screens from [33] reported in Table 2.

464 5. Conclusions

465 A three-dimensional approach is introduced in this work to estimate more accurately the poros-
 466 ity of insect-proof screens from geometric parameters easy to measure. As detected by previous
 467 authors, the standard two-dimensional approach in the literature was not able to explain why
 468 screens with higher porosity did experience also a greater pressure drop. The introduced ap-
 469 proach, which consists of solving a non-linear system of equations and calculate the volume of the
 470 threads per total volume, includes the effect of thickness in the estimation of porosity, providing
 471 more exact results. The approach allows to reconstruct the three-dimensional geometry computa-
 472 tionally, which can be of strong interest to test the aerodynamics of different insect-proof screen
 473 designs *à la carte* with Computational Fluid Dynamics codes.

474 The method has been applied to a total of 20 insect-proof screens, in order to spot the differ-
 475 ences between the two and three-dimensional approach. The analysis has shown that non-linear
 476 interaction between the geometric variables leads to some differences in the trend of results. In
 477 addition, the method has been applied to 6 insect-proof screens to contrast the effect of ageing. In
 478 this investigation (which also included a dedicated uncertainty analysis) it has been evidenced that
 479 volumetric porosity yields more reasonable results than superficial porosity. This sheds light on the
 480 question raised by previous authors on why the expected porosity did not match with the measured
 481 pressure drop in brand new and old&washed insect-proof screens. A limitation of the approach is
 482 that the non-linear models do not include the effect of tension forces in the variation of the diame-

483 ter of the threads (which may not be fully circular cross section yarns due to this) nor a potential
484 gentle increase/decrease in thickness, which is future work. Also, it is very important to provide
485 accurate measurements for the computational estimation of the shape of the interlaced threads
486 and porosity. As discussed in the manuscript, if measurements are not correct, the full geometry
487 may not match for obvious reasons (e.g. an incorrectly measured diameter may be larger than the
488 spacing between threads, being an impossible geometry). Additional experimental work dedicated
489 to the observation through microscope and characterisation of an extensive number of manufac-
490 tured screens (+100) would be very valuable for further validation. Future/current research is also
491 being oriented to the development of aerodynamic models of insect-proof screens, where experi-
492 mental data of pressure drop in wind tunnels is being used to validate such models. It is expected
493 that models including three-dimensional porosity outperforms those with two-dimensional porosity.
494 Thus, future experimental and modelling work is advisable to further demonstrate the potential
495 of the introduced estimation of three-dimensional porosity.

496 The methodology and codes resulting from this work have been implemented in the Poro3D
497 v1.0 software, which is provided as supplementary material. The software allows to obtain straight-
498 forward both 3D and 2D porosities, as well as the full representation of the 3D geometry.

499 **Supplementary Material**

500 The methodology here developed has been implemented in a software (Poro3D v1.0) to obtain
501 instantly the superficial and volumetric porosity from either manual inputs or Euclides software
502 [21] outputs. The Poro3D v1.0 software is provided as supplementary material to this manuscript,
503 which can be downloaded from the website <https://rsoftuma.uma.es/en/software/poro3d/>.

504 **Acknowledgments**

505 The authors acknowledge The Andalusian Research, Development and Innovation Plan (PAIDI
506 - Junta de Andalucía) and the research project UAL2020-AGR-A1916 within the FEDER-Andalucía
507 2014-2020 operational programme.

508 **References**

509 [1] D.L. Valera, L.J. Belmonte, F.D. Molina-Aiz, and A. López. Greenhouse agriculture in
510 almería. a comprehensive techno-economic analysis, Mar 2016.

- 511 [2] A.F. Miguel and A.M. Silva. Porous materials to control climate behaviour of enclosures: an
512 application to the study of screened greenhouses. Energy and Buildings, 31(3):195–209, 2000.
- 513 [3] Meir Teitel. The effect of insect-proof screens in roof openings on greenhouse microclimate.
514 Agricultural and Forest Meteorology, 110(1):13–25, 2001.
- 515 [4] R.A.J Taylor, Sarit Shalhevet, Ishai Spharim, Menachem J Berlinger, and Sarah Lebiush-
516 Mordechi. Economic evaluation of insect-proof screens for preventing tomato yellow leaf curl
517 virus of tomatoes in israel. Crop Protection, 20(7):561–569, 2001.
- 518 [5] Meir Teitel. The effect of screened openings on greenhouse microclimate. Agricultural and
519 Forest Meteorology, 143(3):159–175, 2007.
- 520 [6] M.J. Berlinger, R.A.J. Taylor, S. Lebiush-Mordechi, S. Shalhevet, and I. Spharim. Efficiency
521 of insect exclusion screens for preventing whitefly transmission of tomato yellow leaf curl virus
522 of tomatoes in israel. Bulletin of Entomological Research, 92(5):367–373, 2002.
- 523 [7] Robin V. Gunning and Graham D. Moores. Insensitive Acetylcholinesterase as Sites for
524 Resistance to Organophosphates and Carbamates in Insects: Insensitive Acetylcholinesterase
525 Confers Resistance in Lepidoptera, pages 221–238. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Hei-
526 delberg, 2001.
- 527 [8] P Muñoz, JI Montero, A Antón, and F Giuffrida. Effect of insect-proof screens and roof
528 openings on greenhouse ventilation. Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research, 73(2):171–
529 178, 1999.
- 530 [9] H. Fatnassi, T. Boulard, C. Poncet, and M. Chave. Optimisation of greenhouse insect screening
531 with computational fluid dynamics. Biosystems Engineering, 93(3):301–312, 2006.
- 532 [10] Meir Teitel. Using computational fluid dynamics simulations to determine pressure drops on
533 woven screens. Biosystems Engineering, 105(2):172–179, 2010.
- 534 [11] Alejandro Lopez-Martinez, Diego L. Valera Martínez, Francisco Molina-Aiz, Araceli Peña-
535 Fernandez, and Patricia Marín-Membrive. Microclimate evaluation of a new design of insect-
536 proof screens in a mediterranean greenhouse. Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research,
537 12(2):338, 2014.

- 538 [12] Peeyush Soni, V.M. Salokhe, and H.J. Tantau. Effect of screen mesh size on vertical tem-
539 perature distribution in naturally ventilated tropical greenhouses. Biosystems Engineering,
540 92(4):469–482, 2005.
- 541 [13] Harmanto, H.J. Tantau, and V.M. Salokhe. Microclimate and air exchange rates in green-
542 houses covered with different nets in the humid tropics. Biosystems Engineering, 94(2):239–
543 253, 2006.
- 544 [14] C. Kittas, T. Boulard, T. Bartzanas, N. Katsoulas, and M. Mermier. Influence of an insect
545 screen on greenhouse ventilation. Transactions of the ASAE, 45(4), 2002.
- 546 [15] F.D. Molina-Aiz, D.L. Valera, A.A. Peña, J.A. Gil, and A. López. A study of natural venti-
547 lation in an almería-type greenhouse with insect screens by means of tri-sonic anemometry.
548 Biosystems Engineering, 104(2):224–242, 2009.
- 549 [16] Alejandro López, Diego Luis Valera, and Francisco Molina-Aiz. Sonic anemometry to measure
550 natural ventilation in greenhouses. Sensors, 11(10):9820–9838, 2011.
- 551 [17] A López, Diego Luis Valera Martínez, Francisco Domingo Molina Aiz, and A Peña. Sonic
552 anemometry measurements to determine airflow patterns in multi-tunnel greenhouses. Spanish
553 Journal of Agricultural Research, (3):631–642, 2012.
- 554 [18] Alejandro López-Martínez, Francisco D Molina-Aiz, Diego L Valera-Martínez, Javier López-
555 Martínez, Araceli Peña-Fernández, and Karlos E Espinoza-Ramos. Application of semi-
556 empirical ventilation models in a mediterranean greenhouse with opposing thermal and wind
557 effects. use of non-constant cd (pressure drop coefficient through the vents) and cw (wind
558 effect coefficient). Agronomy, 9(11):736, 2019.
- 559 [19] B.J Bailey, J.I Montero, J.Pérez Parra, A.P Robertson, E Baeza, and R Kamaruddin. Airflow
560 resistance of greenhouse ventilators with and without insect screens. Biosystems Engineering,
561 86(2):217–229, 2003.
- 562 [20] Chris Solomon and Toby Breckon. Fundamentals of digital image processing a practical
563 approach with examples in Matlab. Wiley-Blackwell, 2011.
- 564 [21] AJ Álvarez, RM Oliva, and DL Valera. Software for the geometric characterisation of insect-
565 proof screens. Computers and electronics in agriculture, 82:134–144, 2012.

- 566 [22] V. S. Spiridonov and S. V. Belov. Properties of porous materials composed of metal wire
567 screens with square apertures. i. structural characteristics of materials. Soviet Powder
568 Metallurgy and Metal Ceramics, 24(11):841–845, Nov 1985.
- 569 [23] A López-Martínez, FD Molina-Aiz, DL Valera, and KE Espinoza-Ramos. Models for charac-
570 terising the aerodynamics of insect-proof screens from their geometric parameters. Biosystems
571 Engineering, 192:42–55, 2020.
- 572 [24] C Pérez Vega, JA Ramírez Arias, IL López Cruz, et al. Aerodynamic characteristics of anti-
573 insect mesh windows used in greenhouses in mexico. Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Agrícolas,
574 7(3):493–506, 2016.
- 575 [25] R. A. Pinker and M. V. Herbert. Pressure loss associated with compressible flow through
576 square-mesh wire gauzes. Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science, 9(1):11–23, 1967.
- 577 [26] A. J. Álvarez, R. M. Oliva, A. Jiménez-Vargas, and M. Villegas-Vallecillos. A three-
578 dimensional approach to the porous surface of screens. The Journal of The Textile Institute,
579 110(5):639–646, 2019.
- 580 [27] Frederick Thomas Peirce. 5—the geometry of cloth structure. Journal of the Textile Institute
581 Transactions, 28(3):T45–T96, 1937.
- 582 [28] Bertil Olofsson. 49—a general model of a fabric as a geometric-mechanical structure. Journal
583 of the Textile Institute Transactions, 55(11):T541–T557, 1964.
- 584 [29] Zuhaib Ahmad and Brigita Kolčavová Sirková. Analysis of mutual interlacing of threads
585 in multifilament single layer and two layer woven fabric structure using Fourier series. The
586 Journal of The Textile Institute, 2019.
- 587 [30] Savvas Vassiliadis, Argyro Kallivretaki, Paraskevas Frantzeskakis, and Christopher Provatidis.
588 Macromechanical modelling of woven fabrics. International Journal of Clothing Science and
589 Technology, 2012.
- 590 [31] Savvas Vassiliadis, Argyro Kallivretaki, Dimitra Domvoglou, and Christofer Provatidis. Me-
591 chanical analysis of woven fabrics: The state of the art. 2011.

- 592 [32] Q Wang, B Maze, H Vahedi Tafreshi, and B Pourdeyhimi. On the pressure drop modeling of
593 monofilament-woven fabrics. Chemical engineering science, 62(17):4817–4821, 2007.
- 594 [33] Alejandro López Martínez, Francisco Domingo Molina Aiz, Diego Luis Valera Martínez, Ana
595 Araceli Peña Fernández, and Karlos Espinoza. Effect of material ageing and dirt on the
596 behaviour of greenhouse insect-proof screens. Spanish journal of agricultural research, 16(4):4,
597 2018.
- 598 [34] Luigi Formisano, Antonio Pannico, Christophe El-Nakhel, Giuseppe Starace, Milena Poledica,
599 Stefania De Pascale, and Youssef Rouphael. Improved porosity of insect proof screens enhances
600 quality aspects of zucchini squash without compromising the yield. Plants, 9(10):1264, 2020.
- 601 [35] Meir Teitel. Using Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations to determine pressure drops
602 on woven screens. Biosystems engineering, 105(2):172–179, 2010.
- 603 [36] M Teitel and E Wenger. Improving airflow through insect-proof screens. In International
604 CIPA Conference 2012 on Plastics for a Green Planet 1015, pages 201–207, 2012.
- 605 [37] Lei Yang, Xiaoyu Wu, Dewei Zhao, Hui Li, and Jun Zhai. An improved prewitt algorithm
606 for edge detection based on noised image. In 2011 4th International congress on image and
607 signal processing, volume 3, pages 1197–1200. IEEE, 2011.
- 608 [38] Wenshuo Gao, Xiaoguang Zhang, Lei Yang, and Huizhong Liu. An improved Sobel edge de-
609 tection. In 2010 3rd International conference on computer science and information technology,
610 volume 5, pages 67–71. IEEE, 2010.
- 611 [39] Shigeru Ando. Consistent gradient operators. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and
612 Machine Intelligence, 22(3):252–265, 2000.
- 613 [40] Rajdeep Dhar, Radheshyam Gupta, and KL Baishnab. An analysis of Canny and Laplacian of
614 Gaussian image filters in regard to evaluating retinal image. In 2014 International Conference
615 on Green Computing Communication and Electrical Engineering (ICGCCEE), pages 1–6.
616 IEEE, 2014.
- 617 [41] A López Martínez, Diego Luis Valera Martínez, Francisco Domingo Molina Aiz, Ana
618 Araceli Peña Fernández, and Patricia Marín Membrive. Field analysis of the deterioration

- 619 after some years of use of four insect-proof screens utilized in mediterranean greenhouses.
620 Spanish journal of agricultural research, (4):958–967, 2013.
- 621 [42] Sergio Castellano, Giuseppe Starace, Lorenzo De Pascalis, Marco Lippolis, and Giacomo
622 Scarascia-Mugnozza. Experimental results on air permeability of agricultural nets. Journal
623 of Agricultural Engineering, 47(3):134–141, 2016.
- 624 [43] AJ Álvarez, RM Oliva, A Jiménez-Vargas, and M Villegas-Vallecillos. A three-dimensional
625 approach to the porous surface of screens. The Journal of The Textile Institute, 110(5):639–
626 646, 2019.
- 627 [44] Andrea Saltelli, Stefano Tarantola, Francesca Campolongo, and Marco Ratto. Sensitivity
628 analysis in practice: a guide to assessing scientific models, volume 1. Wiley Online Library,
629 2004.
- 630 [45] F-J Granados-Ortiz and J Ortega-Casanova. Quantifying & analysing mixed aleatoric
631 and structural uncertainty in complex turbulent flow simulations. International Journal of
632 Mechanical Sciences, 188:105953, 2020.
- 633 [46] Francisco-Javier Granados-Ortiz, Carlos Perez Arroyo, Guillaume Puigt, Choi-Hong Lai, and
634 Christophe Airiau. On the influence of uncertainty in computational simulations of a high-
635 speed jet flow from an aircraft exhaust. Computers & Fluids, 180:139–158, 2019.
- 636 [47] Hilde Breesch and Arnold Janssens. Building simulation to predict the performances of natural
637 night ventilation: uncertainty and sensitivity analysis. In Pro. 9th Int. IBPSA Conf, 2005.
- 638 [48] F-J Granados-Ortiz, J Ortega-Casanova, and C-H Lai. Propagation of uncertainty in a ro-
639 tating pipe mechanism to generate an impinging swirling jet flow for heat transfer from a flat
640 plate. Engineering with Computers, pages 1–30, 2020.
- 641 [49] Jing Zhao, Yaoqi Duan, and Xiaojuan Liu. Uncertainty analysis of weather forecast data for
642 cooling load forecasting based on the monte carlo method. Energies, 11(7):1900, 2018.
- 643 [50] Raphael Linker, Moshe Tarnopolsky, and Ido Seginer. Increased resistance to flow and
644 temperature-rise resulting from dust accumulation on greenhouse insect-proof screens. In
645 2002 ASAE Annual Meeting, page 1. American Society of Agricultural and Biological Engi-
646 neers, 2002.